

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF PERSONALITY TRAITS BETWEEN MALE AND FEMALE ON VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The purpose of the present research was to describe and compare the personality traits male female in volleyball player (sociability, extraversion, dominance, self-concept, conventionality, mental toughness, emotional stability) of competitive volleyball game in male and female sports. The method of the study is descriptive analyses, total fifty (Each 25) samples representing both in male and female were selected and to collect the data the standardized scale devised by Dr Ajith Sing has administered on the subject who are participating in all India interuniversity tournament, later 't' test was applied to assess the significant difference in self-concept factor of personality traits between volleyball sportsperson of male and female, the conclusion was drawn that male sportsperson have possessed the high self-concept personality traits comparing to their counterpart, it was rationalized that nature of male participation develops and cultivates the self-concept values and character among the participants volleyball player.

Keywords: personality traits, male and female, volleyball player

1. Introduction

Personality including dimensions of Sport psychology has emerged as a field with a personality including dimensions of neuroticism, research tradition that provides a foundation for direct extraversion, openness, agreeableness and application with volleyball. As the role played by conscientiousness, two that have supported both

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psychological factors in the performance and over well-theoretical and empirical by a large number of researches being of male has become better understood, in the last decades. Numerous studies have intervention have been designed to favourably affect examined the relations between five factor model male behaviour throughout their involvement in sport dimensions and sport activities; these studies suggest and beyond. Sport psychology researchers have been that there is a positive correlation between sport interested in how male' psychological an activities, extraversion and conscientiousness and also a characteristics influence performance. From this point, it negative correlation between sport activities and clear that psychological characteristics differ between neuroticism. Also the results of studies connected with more and less effective male and female. Moreover, the Three-dimensional model of personality have shown ability to mentally prepare is considered a key component correlation between sport activities with one or more of such differences. The optimal level of skills in dimensions of low neuroticism, high extraversion and low championship depends on three factors; physical, skill psychotics. It seems that champion's different women are extraversion and there is a significant relation performance depends on mental preparation, influence of between sport abilities and extraversion rate. It is obvious psychology and personality of sportsmen. So it needs to higher abilities have related with self-concept and lower compare the relationship between psychological variables abilities with introspection. Some findings have found (personality traits) in different sex. This matter would help different results in this case.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

A Comparative Study of Personality Traits between Male and Female of Volleyball Player.

1.2 Hypotheses

It was hypothesized there is a significant difference in self-concept between male and male volleyball players.

1.3 Objective

To assess the significant differences of personality traits between male and female players.

1.4 Materials and methods

The present research is descriptive comparative which compares the personality traits of volleyball player male and female sportsperson.

1.5 Participants

The participants of the present research are belonging the male and female volleyball player those are participating in the inter university tournaments. The sample was selected using purposive random technique, twenty five subjects of each group as male and female sportsperson were selected from volleyball player male and female were evaluated and compared using seven factor personality traits inventories

1.6 Measurement Tools

To collect the requisite data, the standard zed questionnaire constructed by Dr Ajith Sing has administered on the volleyball sportsperson of male and female, who are participating in all India interuniversity tournament held at different part of the country.

1.7 Data analysis

First descriptive statistics including means and standard deviation and 't' test used for describing the personality traits of male and female volleyball sportsperson. The seven primary personality dimension identified by Dr Ajith Singh are described as being functionally independent and psychologically meaningful dimensions of a person's personality. The primary personality factors that are self-concept as taken to prepare research article, hence, self-concept has analysed and described as follows.

2. Discussion

The hypothesis that the male sports person will have better self-concept ability than the female sportsperson is framed on the rationale that the nature of game and participation is believed to be a prime creator of personality traits of male, which also includes the social adjustment. Because normally, the male sportsperson would naturally have advantage over her counterpart as the she or he enjoys self-interaction, receives more self-experience, gets the more rich exposure she gains, would all influence and promote greater amount of characteristics that fit her in a highly stable mentality in which she could easily adjust self himself to the different occasions and rich experience of self and matches would determines personality traits and psychological factors comparing to male volleyball sportsperson.

Table 1: Presenting the mean scores and values of self-concept of male and female sportsperson

Variables	Male	Female
Mean	41.66	36.18
SD	3.78	4.76
t-value	12.72	

*Significant at 0.05 level

The table reveals the mean, SD and 't' values of self-concept of male and female sportsperson and the mean scores of both male and female sportsperson are 41.66 and 36.18. Respectively the higher mean score of male sportsmen indicate the presence of more conventionality nature among them. The obtained 't' value is 12.72 which is highly significant at 0.05 suggests that there is a significant difference in self-concept traits of male and female sportsperson.

Because, male students gets more chances to have a better standard of living, better standard of education, mass media exposure and higher level of interaction with in groups. And mantle setup and attitude towards women education is having negative and not supportive nature, also accessible and congenial to providing quality education. Therefore, the sportsperson have lack of opportunities and not supporting leads to hindrance developing positive self-concept, hence formulated hypothesis is conformed.

3. Conclusion

The male volleyball sportsperson participation in sports activities develops harmonious personality traits among the participants, the study also proved and expressed the nature of attitudes and supportive factors towards higher education and life these would results in developing advantages to cultivate the self-concept values and positive personality traits in the sportsperson, comparing to their counterpart the female sportsperson self-concept is very low level of self-concept among the female.

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